

PRIDE AND LEADERSHIP COMMUNICATION BEHAVIOR

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Abstract. In this article, opinions about lack of arrogance and communication etiquette of the leader are presented. Also, the article mentions some of the author's views, such as the culture of treatment, behavior of the leader, his relationship with the employees of the organization in which he operates, and what kind of culture of treatment he should implement when problems arise.

Keywords. Leader, culture of treatment, arrogance, organization, personnel, employee, problem, standard.

Management of a particular organization is multifaceted, and effective leadership in its various fields requires different approaches and the participation of qualified specialists. We can note the wealth of the organization by dividing it into two main groups - tangible and intangible manifestations. Intangible assets include not only intellectual potential, but also all achievements related to the human factor at the level of this organization. All persons working in a certain organization are called "personnel".[1,15] Psychologist T.Yu. Bazarov's according to definition, "the sum of all human resources in the organization is personnel. This includes employees of the organization, partners participating in the implementation of any project, experts invited to participate in research, strategy development, and implementation of any event. Human resource in the

organization is a subject in the focus of management sciences, and how to achieve the main goal of the organization is related to the competent management of personnel.

Regulatory documents applicable at the level of each organization include job descriptions, internal procedures for the life of this organization, personnel conditions, regulations on organizational departments, career guidelines, "Contract", etc. These regulatory documents greatly facilitate the supervision and evaluation of personnel managers and increase the possibility of self-management of employees and teams.

Socio-psychological aspects of personnel management. In this field, the personnel management service is tasked with selecting candidates for available vacancies, assigning personnel to the workplace, and in-depth study of the personal and professional nature of the employee in matters related to the workplace and profession.

Management of staff adaptation/adjustment. It implies that the employee will adapt to changing conditions or a new workplace and will soon join the life of the team. To lead employees towards the organization's goal, to achieve the organization's goals through employee activity and participation. Motivating employees, i.e. instilling enthusiasm in them to work towards the organization's goal. The main essence of motivation consists in harmonizing the organization's goal and the employee's interests, and this responsible task is usually assigned to the leader.

Training of personnel is the main event for improving his professional skills, and this factor applies not only to professional specialties, but also to the improvement of leadership skills.

Management knowledge is considered to be the main source reflecting the need of the time in many ways. The management process, on the one hand, ensures the integrity of the structure, and on the other hand, allows for its further

improvement and development. Here, two main functions of management are distinguished: goal-directing and organizational functions. A goal-directing function directs the structure toward the goal of further refinement. And the organizational function ensures the internal order of the structure in achieving the goal and the mutual compatibility between its various parts.[2,24]

The above two main management functions are carried out through a series of tasks. For example, when performing the goal-directing function, the activity includes:

- forecasting the result;
- planning activities towards the goal;
- implementation motivations are included. [3,19]

The main part of the leader's activity is the communication process. The processes of ensuring the implementation of the decision, organizing the activities of employees and the organization, monitoring and encouraging the activities of employees are also carried out through communication. There are different types of personal and business communication in science. In this article, we will focus on the nature of business-related communication and the possibilities of its formation.

Management communication is a process of mutual information exchange aimed at directing employees in a certain direction.

The control dialog appears in:

1. Transferring orders and tasks, giving this or that advice to an employee;
2. "Feedback", that is, receiving a report on how the task was performed;
3. To evaluate the performance of subordinates.

A leader who is a good communicator has an increased opportunity to effectively organize his tasks. Organizational tasks such as influencing employees, motivating them, and leading them towards the organization's goals are also provided through skilled communication. The main aspect of the leader's

communication skills is his activity in the field of communication. Goal-oriented, conscious and free execution of this activity are the main signs of how skillfully a person implements the communication process. It is very important for the leader to know the internal laws of the communication process. The means and methods of managing the communication process are expressed by the phrase communication technologies. It is the adoption and situational application of such technologies that ensures freedom of communication. Thoughts on the internal laws of communication make it possible to further expand the scope of business-related interactions and effectively influence others. In this regard, one of the conditions for managing the communication process is its gradual implementation.

When a leader organizes a communication event in the process of management, this process can be called management communication. A full-fledged and properly organized management communication includes the following main stages:

1. Establish communication/contact.
2. Discuss the issue.
3. Search for solutions.
4. Decision making.

Leadership communication that leads to a positive result is carried out in exactly this sequence of the highlighted stages. More precisely, the effective passage of the communication process is largely related to the successive implementation of these stages. Ensuring this condition is primarily the responsibility of the leader, because directing management communication is mainly within his ability. Now, let's take a closer look at the steps listed above.

The main purpose of forming leadership communication is that the leader solves the problems he needs to implement with his employees through this process. For example, we can note many problematic situations, such as leaving

an employee on duty at the office before the New Year's Eve and, in general, engaging an employee in any work that does not fall under his direct responsibility. Of course, there is a simpler way to deal with such organizational situations. In particular, with a simple command, an employee can be forced to undertake almost any work. However, the main factor that determines the quality of the task is how the result of the work will be, how serious the employee is to the task. Therefore, in management communication, it is assumed to increase the employee's responsibility for the task, to strengthen the feeling of hope that the result of the task will be positive.

Description of the stages of leadership communication. Management communication about work begins with establishing contact with the employee. The process of implementing this stage consists of the leader getting answers to two questions:

1. Who is the person in front of me? 2. How is he?

The content of the answers to these two questions indicates how carefully the first stage was performed. Only when the leader receives detailed answers to these two questions can he proceed to the second stage. The answers should express the willingness of the employee to communicate with the manager. In the implementation of the first stage, the leader is required to be observant, sharp minded and able to accurately know the inner state of the person in question.

For example, when answering the first question in the communication stage, the leader needs to know and assume the following knowledge about the person in front of him:

- 1) age;
- 2) specialty, profession;
- 3) how many years he has been working in this organization;
- 4) marital status;
- 5) ability (which tasks he performs well and which he cannot perform);

6) health information, etc.

A leader with this information can entrust any task to an employee with confidence and expect a positive result. In order to get answers to the above questions, the leader should have as much information as possible about the interlocutor before the beginning of the dialogue. The answers to the first question of the contact establishment stage prepare the manager for future communication, and allow to imagine the interlocutor's strengths and weaknesses in advance. The second question of the contact establishment stage requires determining the inner state of the interlocutor, being aware of his inner experiences during the conversation. The appearance of the person in front of us - body position, facial expressions, hand movements and voice intonation - all this gives information about the current state of the person and is a sign of whether he is ready to move on to the main part of the conversation. These indicators of the external appearance of the interlocutor are usually non-verbal, that is, non-verbal aspects of communication and provide true information about the inner state of a person. It is not wrong to say that non-verbal signals, in most cases, are beyond the scope of voluntary control and are an indicator of a person's real feelings, intentions and desires. For example, clasping both hands in front of the chest and crossing the legs on the knees means a closed position, and this position can be interpreted as the interlocutor withdrawing from the conversation. On the contrary, the placement of hands around the sides, open palms, and standing/sitting with legs bent forward means sympathy for the interlocutor and the content of the communication.

The science of modern psychology can describe such knowledge and skills that the use of some of them will help to make the communication environment more positive and to make interactions more alternative. One of the first and permissible steps in this regard is the reflection of a positive state for communication in the leader's appearance and inner world. The signs of

benevolence, sincere attitude, concern for his interests, in turn, affect the awakening of such responses in the employee. If the rapport-building phase does not lead to a positive conclusion to the continuation of the communication, one of the simplest tips is to ask openly about what is bothering the employee and why it is difficult to continue the communication. Often, this method leads to the expected result, and even if the employee does not openly say about the distraction that bothers him, he is motivated to stay alert and attentive in any case. After understanding the other's readiness for communication, it is possible to move to the second stage of this process. The second stage is the main content of the dialogue, in which the issues and problems raised in connection with the work are discussed. The successful passage of this stage, in a certain sense, requires the activity of the leader, the use of special methods of activity. One of the main aspects of discussing an issue is to understand the other person's point of view. Unfortunately, in the process of communication, there are often such cases that both sides have different ideas about the discussed issue. The appearance of such a vision of the problem, unfortunately, will never lead to its solution. Therefore, at this stage of the dialogue, it is necessary to carry out the event of forming a common understanding and even a common view of the issue under discussion. At the second stage, the ability to listen appears as the main condition for understanding the other. Generally, active and passive forms of listening are distinguished. Active listening means showing signs of understanding while perceiving another's point of view. In this case, the interlocutors ask questions related to determining the essence of the issue, and state conclusions regarding the main part of the conversation.

The characteristic of conducting dialogue on a problematic issue is that this process can be considered successful only if a solution is found that satisfies the interests of the parties involved in the dialogue. A decision is made only after a mutually beneficial solution is found, and communication is considered

successful. At the end of the interview, you can draw conclusions, note down the solution once again and make a short comment on the decision made.

The mentioned stages of perception make it possible to form the basis for arousing sympathy towards oneself during communication. And when the time comes, it is possible to overcome the initial impressions that are inappropriately awakened in relation to others, and not to be distracted by their influence.

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